

START OF BEST4SOIL, THE NETWORK OF PRACTITIONERS FOR SHARING KNOWLEDGE ON PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF SOIL BORNE DISEASES

Healthy soils are of major importance for the future of the European horticultural and agricultural crop production. Especially in intensive production systems, **soil borne diseases** are a major factor with a negative impact on soil health. Newly developed best practices and sound crop rotations permit to maintain, improve or re-establish **soil health** in Europe.

The Best4Soil project has started at 12. November 2018 and is now in the phase of creating factsheets, data bases, videos and network activities. With Best4Soil we are building a **community of practice network** across Europe by inter-connecting growers, advisers, educators and researchers. This network promotes **knowledge ready for practice on 4 best practices** (fig. 1, 2, 3, 4) for the control of soil borne diseases. Therefore we build a website and organize meetings and events in 20 European countries where we exchange knowledge on soil health with our communities of practice. The main objective of the Best4Soil thematic network is to maintain, improve or re-establish soil health in Europe. We provide open-access databases with information on the range of pathogens and nematodes that affect vegetable, arable and cover crops to help practitioners to build appropriate **crop rotations** and innovative **control strategies**.

Fig. 1: Compost/
organic amendments

Fig. 2: Green manures /
cover crops

Fig. 3: Anaerobic
disinfestation (ASD)

Fig. 4: (Bio)solarisation

Innovative control strategies are provided through easily understandable tutorial videos and through factsheets which give more in-depth information. All information is edited in 22 EU languages, will be freely accessible and highly comprehensible to guarantee a smooth knowledge transfer from research to practice.

BEST4SOIL PROPOSES THREE APPROACHES FOR OPTIMAL SOIL HEALTH:

the adaptation of **optimised crop rotation** as a basis to prevent build-up of soil borne diseases, which is specific to the needs and situation of each individual grower

the implementation of best practices that have a preventive effect, such as the use of **compost, organic amendments, cover crops and green manures**.

the implementation of best practices which reduce soil borne diseases after they occur, in order to reduce inoculum levels, such as **(bio)solarisation and anaerobic disinfestation (ASD)**.

WWW.BEST4SOIL.EU

We aim to launch our website in January 2020. The website will provide **highly comprehensible information**, a blog and chatroom and **two open access databases** on the range of pathogens (soil borne fungi and nematodes) affecting host plants, which will help the practitioners to build appropriate crop rotations and innovative control strategies.

A **decision support tool** will be developed to aid growers and advisers to plan appropriate crop rotations and the use of green manures/cover crops beneficial for soil health. This support tool will extract tailor made information that is relevant for a particular grower.

EU WIDE NETWORK

With this information, growers can innovate their **soil health management strategies**. Besides the website and databases we create **communities of practice (CoP)** to deal with **specific regional soil health issues**, which we interconnect through our network.

Best4Soil will deploy **local facilitators** to set up the network with active communities of practice. The facilitators in different European regions are organized in **4 subnetworks**, based on the EPPO climatic zones and actively disseminate the knowledge and collection of feedback from practice. The consortium of Best4Soil includes advisers, breeder, communicators, educators, growers, and researchers from eight European countries. Together with facilitators in twelve more EU countries, the network will interconnect an important part of the European growers, advisers and educators, the main stakeholders of Best4Soil.

To get involved or for more information you can contact us by e-mail:

☛ Info@Best4Soil.eu

THE BEST4SOIL NETWORK IN 20 COUNTRIES

Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

